

FACTORS EFFECTING ADOPTION OF DIGITAL MARKETING BY MICRO ENTREPRENEURS OF RURAL SOUTH ODISHA.

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Abstract:

Digital Marketing has emerged as one of the greatest tools of marketing in the modern world. Not only it has brought down the marketing expenses through its efficiency but has also helped the entrepreneurs in engaging with the customers more effectively. It also helps in collecting and analysing the data on customers behaviour so that the entrepreneurs can make more efficient strategies for attainment of their business goals. (Sheoliha et al 2023). Various studies have been done on use of Digital marketing by entrepreneurs. However, the utilisation of Digital marketing options by rural micro entrepreneurs of India is still a field to be explored.

Purpose of study: Presented study aims at Identifying the factors effecting the adoption of Digital Marketing by micro entrepreneurs of rural South Odisha.

Methodology used: The study employs the combination of UTAUT and TOE model. It is done based on the primary data collected from 386 respondents from the region. The data is then subjected to Exploratory factor analysis for factor extraction and regression analysis for hypothesis testing.

Outcome: The outcome of the study suggests that the factors like Performance expectancy, Effort expectancy, Technological factors, Organisational factors, and Environmental factors impact the adoption of Digital marketing by micro entrepreneurs of rural South Odisha.

Keywords: Digital marketing, micro entrepreneurs, rural entrepreneurs, rural micro entrepreneurs, rural micro entrepreneurs of India, South Odisha.

1. Introduction:

Promoting products and services "through the use of digital technology, most notably the internet, mobile phones, display advertising, and any other digital medium" is known as digital marketing (DM) [Smith, A.N et al 2012]. Digital platforms support active information and efficient inventory control. The way marketers engage with consumers has evolved as a result of digital platforms. Online advertising has grown at an exponential rate thanks to the increasing use of smartphones and PCs. On social media (SM) platforms including Facebook, YouTube, Twitter, Instagram, Snapchat, Pinterest, and LinkedIn, advertisers spent USD 51.3 billion in 2017 [Solakis, K et al 2022]. Digital advertisements brought in USD 273 billion, or 44% of the total USD 629 billion in advertising spending in 2018 [Nhuvera, C.E.; Dorasamy, N. 2021, Hedau 2024]. Direct marketing may achieve growth goals like higher revenue, more

brand exposure, more customer contact, and more lead generation by effectively targeting particular demographics. Advertising budget imbalances have increased as a result [Eid, R.; El-Gohary, H. **2013**].

Buying and selling goods online has always been made easier with direct messaging, regardless of the delivery method. The third wave of technological development that really sparked an information revolution was the internet [Hedau 2020; Solakis, K et al **2022**; Ahmad et al 2023]. DM representation includes a range of goods, services, and marketing approaches. This kind of marketing makes use of a variety of digital media.

Stakeholders can communicate digitally at any moment. DM's main objective is to draw in new clients and give them a way to interact with the company [He, W.; Wang, F.-K.; Zha, S. **2014**]. DM includes search engine optimisation, text message marketing, affiliate marketing, social media, email marketing, and internet advertising.

Rather than smaller businesses and organisations, the bulk of the DM literature concentrates on larger ones [Ritz, W.; Wolf, M.; McQuitty, S **2019**]. Small businesses need to build mobile-friendly websites, and they need outside expertise to help handle these tasks. Due to economic constraints, 55% of small US businesses do not have a website [Pandey, N et al **2020**]. Small businesses in the US frequently lack websites because of financial limitations [Nuseira, M.T.; Aljumahb A. **2020**].

Companies need to stay current with technology developments. This is especially true for SMEs (small and medium-sized enterprises) in emerging nations [Ritz, W.; Wolf, M.; McQuitty, S **2019**]. India, is working to increase the use of information and communications technology (ICT) in enterprises, especially small and medium-sized ones. Therefore, a strong ICT infrastructure is essential to the competitiveness of SMEs.

Developments in digital infrastructure that allow both fixed and mobile Internet access have made it easier for people to use the Internet. but that doesn't mean that digital communications has improved universally. (Ofcom, 2016, p3). Many isolated rural locations in affluent economies are falling behind in terms of digital infrastructure provision and capabilities (see, for example, Riddlesden and Singleton, 2014; Philip et al., 2017).

The factors that affect SMEs' and startups' adoption of digital marketing in both developed and developing nations have been the subject of numerous prior studies. While the limitations imposed by infrastructural, economic, Social and educational inadequacies in rural areas (Goel R. 2024) makes it very important to understand the factors that effects the adoption of Digital Marketing by Rural Entrepreneurs.

This study focus on understanding the same for the micro entrepreneurs of south Odisha through quantitative approach based on UTAUT theory. The primary data is collected through convenience sampling and is subjected to exploratory factor analysis through SPSS and then the hypothesis is tested through linear regression analysis done on SPSS.

By concentrating on digital marketing in the rural South Odisha, this study closes a gap in the existing literature and offers insights that could be used in other rural areas of India. This study adds to academics, managers, entrepreneurs, and business owners' scientific grasp of digital marketing. Conversely, this study helps Micro small and start-up companies identify the factors that affect digital marketing acceptance, which enables them to grow and solve a range of issues.

2. Literature review:

2.1: Digital Marketing

Digital marketing is the use of technology in marketing processes to better understand customers by catering to their demands. Using smartphones, laptops, and other gadgets to connect with clients via social media, websites, applications, and other channels is known as online marketing. There is a great deal of promise in digital marketing. Finding out how customers use the newest technology and applying that knowledge to the company's advantage is one of the key objectives of internet marketing. This enables the user to communicate with potential customers more successfully. Companies in industrialised nations now understand the importance of digital marketing. To succeed, businesses will need to combine both traditional and online methods (Bala & Verma, 2018).

2.2: Digital Marketing in India

India ranks second with almost half of its population (**49.15%**) using the internet – which counts as **692 million** people, following China with 1.05 billion people using internet there (74.36% of its population) [explodingtopics 2023]. No wonder that the online advertisement and shopping in India is growing year by year. Young people who utilise the internet and have steadily rising socioeconomic status invest more time and money in digital activities, which influences the preferences of their clientele.

Books, electronics, travel, financial services, clothing, and cosmetic products are among the often purchased goods and services on the internet. Although the Internet only makes up a small percentage of India's GDP at the moment, retailers believe a boom in the Internet is imminent (Sharma & Thakur, 2020).

2.3: Advantages of Digital Marketing for entrepreneurs

Digital Marketing has revolutionised the marketing practices in several manners. It has brought so many benefits to the users that today a business without digital marketing is considered to be impractical. Some of the benefits that Digital Marketing provides to the entrepreneurs are: **Better reach** to the customers through various platforms like Meta, Google, Instagram and so on. Digital marketing helps you to reach directly to the customers mobile or computer anywhere in the world. **Better targeting of the customers** as digital marketing makes it possible to identify the target group on the basis of their online activities and interest recorded, hence filtering the irrelevant people at the marketing stage only. (Fachrurazi, F et al 2022). It **reduces the cost of marketing** for micro entrepreneurs by promoting the products on virtual platforms which reduces the cost of printing and distribution as in traditional methods. (Fachrurazi, F et al 2022). **Better marketing analytics** is available for future follow-up and retargeting. This helps in gaining depth in market. **Less efforts required** as compared to traditional marketing. Digital Marketing can be done using a computer or mobile sitting anywhere in the world at any point of time. **Real-time customer service** by Giving customers assistance to solve their problems and emphasising their significance (Yamini & Chand, 2020). **Better Competitive Advantages** are there for small and micro entrepreneurs with lesser budget and resources (Kano, K et al 2022).

2.4: Micro Entrepreneurs in India

In India, the term "micro entrepreneur" describes people or tiny companies that function at the micro level; they typically have few employees and less resources. These micro-enterprises work in a variety of industries, including small-scale vending, repair services, and other business ventures (Olaposi, 2021). They are mostly engaged in unorganised industries and are essential to the Indian economy since they generate jobs, encourage creativity, and aid in the reduction of poverty and advancement of the economy.

MSME Act of India as modified in 2020 does not differentiate between Micro enterprises based on manufacturing and service sector. An organisation is considered to micro enterprise if its annual turnover is not more than 50 million INR, or the investment in plant and machinery is not more than 10 million INR irrespective of the sector it belongs to. (MSME classification by GOI)

2.5 Rural Areas

In India, 'countryside' or 'village' are other terms for rural areas. There is hardly any population density there. The main sources of income in rural areas are agriculture, cottage industries, fishing, ceramics, etc. Today, virtually all Indian economic agencies define rural India differently. Here are a few examples: A town with a maximum population of 15,000 is deemed to be rural in nature by the Planning Commission. The panchayat is the decision-making body in these places. The panchayat is composed of five individuals. "Rural" is defined by the National Sample Survey Organisation (NSSO) as:

- An area with a population density of no more than 400 people per square kilometre.
- Villages lacking a municipal board but having well-defined survey borders;
- At least 75% of working-age males engaged in agriculture or related fields.

RBI definition says that rural areas are the areas with a population less than 49,000 (tier -3 to tier-6 cities).

Up to 70% of Indians are thought to reside in rural areas. India's rural economies contribute significantly to the country's GDP through the construction, self-employment, agricultural, and service sectors. Monthly per capita expenditure, a stringent metric employed by the National Sample Survey in its 63rd round, states that rural spending makes up 55% of all national monthly spending. Currently, one-third of all Indian FMCG sales come from the rural population. (Dhanlaxmi bank report 2020)

3: Theoretical Framework:

Over the past few decades, research on human-technology interaction has mostly focused on understanding the factors that influence technological acceptability. The earlier work by Azjen [Ajzen, I.; Madden, T.J. 1986] regarding their theory of reasoned action (TRA) led to the creation of the technology acceptance model (TAM; Davis et al. 1989). The Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) posits that an individual's intention to engage in a particular behaviour

is heavily impacted by that intention, which is influenced by attitudes towards the behaviour and subjective norms—a social pressure to engage in the behaviour or abstain from it [Ajzen, I.1991].

It is believed that the technology acceptance model (TAM), which gauges how rapidly new technologies are embraced, is a trustworthy instrument. Numerous research projects have been launched in an attempt to ascertain the benefits and drawbacks of information and communications technology (ICT) use by older persons, as well as the driving forces behind it. The curiosity in this phenomenon has led to the development of many theories and models of technology acceptability and practical utilisation during the past few decades [Maranguni'c, N.; Grani'c, A.2015]. In academic research, the technology acceptance model (TAM) and its extension are frequently employed as measurement instruments [Petrov'ci'c, A.; Petri'c, G.; Manfreda, K.L.2016, Hardill, I.; MacDonald, S. 2000]. Fishbein and Ajzen's theory of reasonable action (TRA) and Ajzen's theory of planned behaviour (TPB) [Ajzen, I.1991] served as the foundation for Fred Davis' initial presentation of TAM [Davis, F.D.; Bagozzi, R.P.; Warshaw, P.R.1989]. It is a widely accepted paradigm that is used to anticipate and explain the effects of people's adoption of technology [Guner, H.; Acarturk, C.2020]. As essential and distinctive features that influence decisions about the use of technology, perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use are identified in the basic Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) [Hardill, I.; MacDonald, S. 2000, Venkatesh, V. et al 2003]. They also serve as a mediator in the intricate relationship between system attributes (external constructs) and prospective system utilisation (attitude and behavioural intention). Since then, some research have proposed using the extended variations of TAM to adapt to different study aims. For instance, these studies have indicated that the extended variations of TAM can better fit their specific study purposes by adding variables like effort expectancy, learning difficulty perception, and social influence [Ahmad, M.O.; Markkula, J.; Oivo, M. 2013, Hogeboom, D.L et al 2010]. The unified theory of acceptance and use of technology (UTAUT), which includes TAM2 and TAM3, combines various technology models with the various TAM versions [Venkatesh, V. et al 2003, Venkatesh, V. et al 2016, Venkatesh, V.; Thong, J.Y.; Xu, X.2012]. Consistent empirical research and a strong theoretical foundation serve as the foundation for the TOE framework. Thus, it is the powerful both that are being used in ICT innovation fields. The TOE framework has been proposed by Alatawi et al (2013) as a viable option in studies that look at IT adoption from an organisational perspective.

Looking into the requirements of the current study, we are using the combinations of factors provided in UTAUT and TOE as the base of the study. The factors taken for the study includes Performance expectancy, Efforts required, Technological context, Organisational context, Environmental context.

3.1: Performance expectancy

Performance expectancy is a model used to describe how much an individual expects the design of their surroundings to support them in efficiently and profitably completing their daily duties [Venkatesh, V et al 2003, Ghalandari, K. 2012]. Performance expectancy in the context of M-

technology refers to the technology's utility [Chao, C.-M.2019, Nikolopoulou, K.et al 2021]. Through social interaction, it provides users with location-independent access to information at any time. The primary factor influencing a user's behavioural intention to accept M-technology is performance expectancy [Onaolapo, S.; Oyewole, O.2018]. Nyembezi [Nyembezi, N.; Bayaga, A. 2014] asserts that older individuals' performance expectations rise in proportion to their ambition to utilise M-technology. The variables considered here are, perceived relative advantage (of using Digital Marketing), Relevance (of using Digital Marketing) to the business goal, and perceived risk (in using Digital Marketing).

***Hypothesis 1:** Performance expectancy is directly related to the adoption of Digital Marketing by micro-entrepreneurs of south Odisha*

3.2: Efforts Expectancy

Theoretically, effort expectancy refers to how much people believe they can profit from the system with less significant psychological work [Venkatesh, V et al 2003, Milošević, et al 2015]. Alraja et al. [Alraja, M.N. et al 2016] state that self-efficacy plus user-friendliness add up to effort expectancy. In order to effectively utilise and apply technology, one must possess a complete understanding of its principles and advantages, as well as a conviction that it helps them satisfy their desires and requirements [Abdallah, N.; Abdallah, O.; Bohra, O. 2021, Maiga, G.; Namagembe, F. 2014]. Self-efficacy and simplicity of use are potent factors that significantly impact the user's behavioural intention to accept or reject the system, according to Milošević et al. [Milosevic, D.; Andrei, S.; Vishny, R.W. 2015]. To ascertain a person's opinions regarding the use of technology, effort expectancy is required [Mcmanus, P.; Standing, C.; Zanolli, R. 2009]. Hence the variables here are complexity (of the process of digital marketing), Compatibility (of the process with the skill set of team available) and the availability of vendors (for outsourcing the digital marketing services).

***Hypothesis 2:** Effort expectancy is directly related to the adoption of Digital Marketing by micro-entrepreneurs of south Odisha*

3.3: Technological Context

According to earlier research on IT adoption that used a TOE framework (e.g., Grover, 1993; Iacovou et al., 1995; Thong, 1999), an organization's technological environment typically explains the characteristics of IT innovation that have an impact on the organization's adoption of IT innovation (Chau and Tam, 1997; Thong, 1999). In this study 3 characters considered are availability of IT Infrastructure, Technical Knowhow, and perceived trend (regarding use of Digital Marketing in the industry).

***Hypothesis 3:** Technological factors are directly related to the adoption of Digital Marketing by micro-entrepreneurs of south Odisha.*

3.4: Organisational Context

According to the Technology Acceptance Framework (TOE) (Chau and Tam, 1997; Tornatzky and Fleischer, 1990), the organisational context, which outlines the attributes of an organisation that impact the organisational adoption of technological innovation, may have an impact on the adoption of technological innovation within the organisation. Innovation is also aided by the availability of knowledgeable personnel, advisors, and other providers of technology services (Rees et al., 1984). On the basis of the literature available 4 variables – firm size (in terms of number of employees), financial resources (allocated by organisation for the purpose), training and support (provided by the top management), and team readiness (for adoption of digital marketing) are considered for this study.

***Hypothesis 4:** Organisational factors are directly related to the adoption of Digital Marketing by micro-entrepreneurs of south Odisha*

3.5: Environmental Context

The industry structure, the existence or lack of technology service providers, and the dogmatic atmosphere are all included in the environmental context. For instance, the intense competition that promotes the adoption of innovation is one way that industrial structure has been studied (Mansfield, 1968; Mansfield et al., 1977).

According to Kamath and Liker (1994), dominant firms within the value chain have the ability to influence their peers to innovate. Innovation is also influenced by the technological support system. Labor-saving innovations are more likely to be mandated for organisations that pay high salaries to skilled personnel (Globerman, 1975; Levin et al., 1987). Lastly, depending on whether its policies promote or inhibit innovation, government regulation may have a positive or negative effect on organisations (Baker, 2011).

Hence the variables taken under this factor are competitive pressure, composite Participation and support from government.

***Hypothesis 5:** Environmental factors are directly related to the adoption of Digital Marketing by micro-entrepreneurs of south Odisha*

Hence the conceptual model for the study is as follows:

4. Methodology:

The items in the construct of this study are taken from previous studies. This is to ensure the content validity. For instance, the items of Performance expectancy are taken from Rogers (1983), Fichman, R. G., & Kemerer, C. F. (1997), Dinev, T., & Hart, P. (2006), Hedau & Joshi (2015) Mishra & Mohanty, (2009) and Gouda, S. K., Patro, Y. S. S., & Mishra, S. (2024). While those of organisational context are taken from Chong et al (2005) and Eze, S. C et al (2020). The variables of efforts expectancy is derived from Rogers (1983). Technological factors are adopted from Kimaro, H. C., & Nhampossa, J. L. (2005), Rogers (1983), and Xu, X., Zhang, W., & Barkhi, R. (2010). Environmental context items are taken from Chong et al (2005). The table below summarises the list of factors from literature.

Factors	Reference
Performance expectancy	Rogers (1983), Fichman, R. G., & Kemerer, C. F. (1997), and Dinev, T., & Hart, P. (2006)
Organisational Context	Chong et al (2005) and Eze, S. C et al (2020).
Efforts Expectancy	Rogers (1983).
Technological Factors	Kimaro, H. C., & Nhampossa, J. L. (2005), Rogers (1983), and Xu, X., Zhang, W., & Barkhi, R. (2010)
Environmental Context	Chong et al (2005)

Table.1.0 List of factors and literature reference.

The questionnaire for the study was formed and data was collected Responses were collected on the likert scale of 5 where the values are as follows:

1= Strongly Disagree, 2= Disagree, 3= Neutral, 4= Agree, and 5= Strongly Agree.

Responses were collected in 4th quarter of 2023 from the south Odisha districts of Malkangiri, Koraput, Nabarangpur, Rayagada, Gajapati, Kalahandi, Kandhamal, and Nuapada. Total responses collected are 423 out of which around 386 were found to be fit for analysis.

5. Analysis

The reliability study was done using the pilot sample of 193 Items (Originally 202 but 9 deleted)

Chronbach's Alfa:

Scale -1 (Organisational factors)

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.902	.903	4

Scale 2 (Performance expectancy)

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.985	.986	4

Scale 3 (Efforts required)

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.957	.957	4

Scale 4 (Technological Factors)

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.996	.996	4

Scale 5 (Environmental Factors)

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.986	.986	4

Scale 6 (Adoption of Digital Marketing)

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.984	.984	3

Further to proceed with Exploratory factor analysis we first conducted KMO and Bartley Test.

The value of the KMO and Bartle test obtained are as follows:

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		0.889
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	18845.932
	df	253
	Sig.	.000

As the value of KMO and Bartlett’s test is above 0.5 and the significance value is less than 0.05, Hence the validity of the scales is well established.

To extract the factors and to test the hypothesis we conducted Exploratory Factor Analysis, using the principal component method and varimax rotation in SPSS.

Following results were obtained:

Rotated Component Matrix					
	Component				
	1	2	3	4	5
Organisational Constraints					
OF1					0.879
OF2					0.84
OF3					0.881
OF4					0.816
Performance Expectancy					
PE1			0.941		
PE2			0.96		
PE3			0.949		
PE4			0.961		
Efforts Required					
ER1				0.937	
ER2				0.945	
ER3				0.933	
ER4				0.943	
Technological Context					
TC1	0.983				
TC2	0.975				
TC3	0.985				
TC4	0.983				
Environmental Context					
EC1		0.978			
EC2		0.976			
EC3		0.967			
EC4		0.962			
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.					
Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.					
a. Rotation converged in 5 iterations.					

The result of each the regression analysis is as follows:

Hypothesis 1: Performance expectancy is directly related to the adoption of Digital Marketing by micro-entrepreneurs of south Odisha

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	445.132	1	445.132	32.527	.000 ^b
	Residual	5255.055	384	13.685		
	Total	5700.187	385			

a. Dependent Variable: Adoption_of_DM

b. Predictors: (Constant), Performance_Expectancy

Hypothesis 2: Effort expectancy is directly related to the adoption of Digital Marketing by micro-entrepreneurs of south Odisha

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	63.542	1	63.542	4.329	.038 ^b
	Residual	5636.644	384	14.679		
	Total	5700.187	385			

a. Dependent Variable: Adoption_of_DM

b. Predictors: (Constant), Efforts_Required

Hypothesis 3: Technological factors are directly related to the adoption of Digital Marketing by micro-entrepreneurs of south Odisha.

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	511.018	1	511.018	37.815	.000 ^b
	Residual	5189.169	384	13.513		
	Total	5700.187	385			

a. Dependent Variable: Adoption_of_DM

b. Predictors: (Constant), Technological_context

Hypothesis 4: Organisational factors are directly related to the adoption of Digital Marketing by micro-entrepreneurs of south Odisha

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	471.471	1	471.471	34.625	.000 ^b
	Residual	5228.716	384	13.616		
	Total	5700.187	385			

a. Dependent Variable: Adoption_of_DM

b. Predictors: (Constant), Organisational_Factors

Hypothesis 5: Environmental factors are directly related to the adoption of Digital Marketing by micro-entrepreneurs of south Odisha

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	469.084	1	469.084	34.434	.000 ^b
	Residual	5231.102	384	13.623		
	Total	5700.187	385			

a. Dependent Variable: Adoption_of_DM

b. Predictors: (Constant), Environmental_Context

In the above regression analysis, we can see that for all the five hypothesis the significance value is less than 0.05. Hence, we can infer that all the hypothesis are accepted.

6. Results and Discussion:

Cronbach's alpha is used to assess the reliability of a scale by evaluating the extent to which multiple items that propose to measure the same general construct produce similar scores. High values of Cronbach's alpha suggest that the items have relatively high internal consistency. $\alpha \geq 0.7$ is called good and $\alpha \geq 0.9$ is called Excellent. As we have received $\alpha \geq 0.9$ hence the reliability of the scale is established.

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) Measure of Sampling Adequacy, and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity are both statistical tests used to assess the suitability of data for factor analysis. According to many studies the value of KMO shall be more than 0.5 (Norisis 2008, li et al 2011, Field 2013) The value of KMO test for the scale used is 0.689. The Significance value of Bartlett's test of sphericity shall be is less than 0.05 (Chan 2010). The analysis says the value to be well below the same and hence the sample passes the test of Adequacy and Corelation Matrix.

To extract the factors from the data, Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) was done. In the EFA table, items OF1 to OF 4 shows Organisational Factors, Items PE1 to PE4 are related to Performance Expectancy, Items ER1 to ER4 are for Efforts Required, Items TC1 to TC 4 are related to Technological context, while Items EC1 to EC 4 are related to Environmental Context, similarly ADM1 to ADM3 items are to measure Adoption of Digital Marketing.

While the exploratory factor analysis established the factors, to test our hypothesis we further did Regression analysis for each hypothesis representing the relation of each independent variable with the dependent variable. Regression analysis is a statistical method used to examine the relationships between a dependent variable (often called the outcome or response variable) and one or more independent variables (also called predictors, covariates, or

explanatory variables). The goal is to model the relationship between the variables, allowing for prediction, explanation, and sometimes causal inference.

The results obtained from regression analysis for all 5 variables shows the significant relationships between the Independent variables and the dependent variable ($p < 0.05$) (Brereton RG 2019). Hence the following hypothesis are accepted.

Hypothesis 1: Performance expectancy is directly related to the adoption of Digital Marketing by micro-entrepreneurs of south Odisha - Accepted

Hypothesis 2: Effort expectancy is directly related to the adoption of Digital Marketing by micro-entrepreneurs of south Odisha - Accepted

Hypothesis 3: Technological factors are directly related to the adoption of Digital Marketing by micro-entrepreneurs of south Odisha. - Accepted

Hypothesis 4: Organisational factors are directly related to the adoption of Digital Marketing by micro-entrepreneurs of south Odisha - Accepted

Hypothesis 5: Environmental factors are directly related to the adoption of Digital Marketing by micro-entrepreneurs of south Odisha - Accepted

7. Conclusion:

The objective of this study is to identify the impact of factors like Performance expectancy, Effort expectancy, Technological factors, Organisational factors, and Environmental factors on adoption of digital marketing by the micro entrepreneurs of rural South Odisha. To identify the same 5 hypothesis were taken and the research was done using the primary data collected from the region. The analysis of the collected data using the methods of EFA and regression analysis establishes the impact of independent variables on the dependent variables. The outcome of the research indicates that the rural micro entrepreneurs are willing to adopt and utilise the digital marketing options if proper infrastructure and support is provided by the government. The technical knowhow regarding the digital marketing tools is also to be promoted. Hence it may be recommended to the policy makers to ensure better digital infrastructure and possible promotional subsidies for the rural areas. At the same time the Digital marketing Industry leaders need to make the tools more user friendly and easy to use with basic affordable advertising plans. The research can be taken further to determine the model fit using the confirmatory factor analysis. The Presented study is limited to the micro entrepreneurs from rural areas of South Odisha. As India is a country with varied culture and beliefs, hence a more comprehensive study can be done to establish the factors that effect the adoption of Digital Marketing among the micro entrepreneurs of various rural areas of the country.

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